

EFFECT OF ILLUMINATION AND SCLEROTIA SIZE ON THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT
OF *Pleurotus tuberregium* (Fr.)Singer

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ABSTRACT

Effect of illumination and sclerotia size on the growth and development of *Pleurotus tuberregium* was investigated. The cultivation was done using the sclerotia on garden soil. Mean fresh weight production by the mushroom was highest, 28.75 ± 1.24 g in the set up under shade and from the 25g sclerotia. While the least was 8.60 ± 0.44 g in the dark from 10g sclerotia. Mean stipe length was greatest 7.30 ± 0.71 cm in the dark from the 20g sclerotia, while the least stipe length, 2.06 ± 0.45 cm from 25g sclerotia. 9.95 ± 0.39 cm was the highest cap diameter observed in 25g sclerotia with the least cap diameter of 2.90 ± 0.59 cm in the dark and from 25g sclerotia. This results shows that extremely high temperature and darkness has a retarding effect on the stipe length and cap development respectively. Therefore shade is the ideal condition for the growth and development of *Pleurotus tuberregium* regardless of sclerotia size.

KEYWORDS: Illumination, Darkness, *Pleurotus tuberregium*, Sclerotia, Garden soil,

INTRODUCTION

A Mushroom is a macrofungus with a distinctive fruiting body which can be either epigeous (above ground) or hypogeous (underground) and large enough to be seen with the naked eye and to be picked by hand. (Chang and Miles, 2004). The edible ones are highly nutritive when compared with meat, egg and milk. They are known to contain a lot of water, protein, lipids, sugars, amino-acids, glycogen, vitamins (B, C and D) and mineral elements (Ghosh and Chakravarty, 1990). Mushrooms represent one of the world's greatest untapped resources of nutritious food. The cultivation of saprophytic edible mushrooms may be the only current economical biotechnology for Lignocellulose organic waste recycling that combines production of protein-rich food with the reduction of environmental pollution (Obodai *et al*, 2004). Cultivation of these edible fungi in the continent is very limited, it is only common in Zimbabwe, Kenya and South Africa (Declaire, 1978). It is still very skeletal in Nigeria. Although many eat mushrooms, they collect them from the wild. This practice is fraught with danger of collecting poisonous species along with the edible ones.

Pleurotus is a genus of gilled mushrooms which includes one of the most widely eaten mushroom, the Oyster mushroom. Like all other basidiomycetes, it is distinguished by having clamp connections along its hyphal length. *Pleurotus* means "side ear". The genus *Pleurotus* has many edible species that have been extensively studied. They are found in both temperate and tropical countries of the world. *Pleurotus tuberregium* is a very popular mushroom in Nigeria that has the potential of being commercialized. It produces tuberous sclerotia in dead wood (Oso, 1977). The fruit body and sclerotia are eaten in Nigeria where they are used for soup and tradomedical preparations, (Oso, 1977).

P. tuberregium is indigenous to tropical Africa and the Australasian pacific regions of the wood (Isikhuemhen *et al*, 2000) including sub-Saharan Africa, Madagascar, Malaysia, Papua New Guinea, Northern Australia, New Caledonia, Indonesia, Myanmar and the Yunnan province of China. Demand for sclerotia all over the world remains high while harvest from the wild is reduced. Deforestation and the conversion of forest into agricultural fields have led to the decline of natural habitat of this mushroom. The resultant scarcity of this mushroom has made it expensive, especially during the dry season (October to April), when it is not easy to collect them in the wild.

During the rainy season, it is possible to see a decaying log filled with fruiting mushrooms during early years of its colonization. Once the substrate is fully colonized and has reached an advanced stage of decay, sclerotia will form at the end of the rainy season. The sclerotia survives the dry and hot season until the rain returns, at which point the sclerotia will either continue to enlarge or form sporophores (mushroom).

Sclerotia are compact masses of mycelia tissue that serves to store food during unfavourable conditions and able to fruit when favourable conditions return. Sclerotia are dark brown on the surface, white inside, spherical to ovoid in shape and as large as 30cm in diameter.

The sclerotia stage is not common among white-rot fungi. Among cultivated mushrooms, only *Morchella* spp. is known to form sclerotia as part of their life cycle. However, only the sclerotia of *P. tuberregium* are valued as food and medicine independent of its ability to produce mushroom. Although it is a sclerotia forming mushroom, some strains from Australia and Indonesia have been observed to fruit directly without ever forming sclerotia (Isikhuemhen 2000a). The sclerotia stage provides a unique advantage to the cultivation of this species. The reason is that it stores for years without loss of viability and eliminates the need for costly fruiting conditions.

Indigenous people of Nigeria incorporate collected mushrooms, including *P.tuberregium* into their diet and medicine (Oso, 1977; Ogundana and Fagade, 1982; Akpaja *et al*; 2003). Similarly, people in Ghana, Cameroun, and the republic of Benin (Obodai *et al*, 2004; Kuyper *et al*; 2002) collect wild mushrooms and use them as food and medicine. Studies have shown that the Igbo people of Nigeria are the major consumers of *P.tuberregium* throughout the country using the fungus in place of meat as well as for its medicinal properties (Akpaja *et al*, 2003). The whitish inner tissue is milled into paste which is used to substitute in part or whole for melon seed (*Citrus lanatus*) in the preparation, of 'Egusi' soup or mixed with corn flour and fried (Isikhuemhen and Okhuoya, 1995; Nwokolo, 1987). Analysis of both sclerotia and sporophores shows that they are rich in carbohydrate, protein, vitamins and minerals while low in fats (Nwokolo, 1987; Okhuoya and Ajerio, 1988)

Pleurotus tuberregium is cultivated either by inoculation of substrate with the pure spawn or by the use of sclerotia to induce sporophore production. Okhuoya and Okogbo (1990) reported that the use of casing material increases yield on a variety of substrates. Mushroom yield is approximately 25% of sclerotia weight and 90% moisture.

Okhuoya and Okogbo (1990) reported studies on sclerotium production in the wild and the induction of sclerotium production in the laboratory.

This study was undertaken to determine the effect of illumination and sclerotia size on the growth and development of *P.tuberregium*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source of sclerotia and preparation

Sclerotia of *Pleurotus tuberregium* were bought from a woman who collected them from decaying logs in the Okomu forest in the Benin region and brought them to the Ekiuwa market for sale. 45 plastic rubber plates of dimension 6cm by 16cm each were obtained from Oba market in Benin City. Knife was also purchased from Oba market. The knife was used to, not only, peel off the brown outer covering of the sclerotia but also to cut the sclerotia into various masses. The weights were then obtained with the aid of the electric weighing balance. The various weight of the sclerotia that were taken are 5g, 10g, 15g, 20g, and 25g. Three replicates were taken for each weight. The weighed sclerotia were then soaked in water for 5 hours.

Preparation of substratum

Loamy soil obtained from the Junior staff Quarter (JSQ) of the University of Benin, Benin-city. Electric soldering iron was purchased from the market at ring road, Benin City. Electric weighing balance obtained

from the Departmental laboratory, Department of Plant Biology and Biotechnology, University of Benin, Benin City. The sieve was used to filter the soil for fine particles. The electric soldering iron was connected to a power source and was used to bore holes at the bottom of the plastic plates to provide for proper aeration and prevent water-logging of the plastic container. The perforated plates were filled with the sieved soil to the brim and then watered a little.

Sowing of sclerotia pieces and planting

After soaking, the various sclerotia were cultivated in the soil inside the perforated plastic rubber plates at a depth of 4cm from the soil surface.

Post planting operation

Distilled water was used for watering throughout the period of experiment. The experimental set-up was three (3) replicates for each mass for three (3) different lightening conditions which are given thus:

1. Total darkness condition, which was provided for by covering with black cellophane.
2. Shade which was obtained by placing in the mushroom house in the Department.
3. Direct sun light which was obtained by placing in the open field.

Distilled water was used for watering at a rate of 40ml/sclerotia during the experiment. The following data were subsequently obtained; time of primordial emergence, cap diameter, stipe length, fresh weight and dry weight.

Data Analysis

The results obtained were analyzed using simple descriptive statistical parameters like mean and standard error. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was also calculated.

RESULTS

The sclerotia of *Pleurotus tuberregium* grew successfully and directly into the sporophores regardless of the different illumination systems and the variation in sclerotia size. There was variation in the time of primordial emergence, morphometric measurements and sporophore yield for the different illumination system and sclerotia sizes.

Primordial emergence was first observed simultaneously in the open field and shaded experiments. In the open field, sclerotia of size 20g emerged first with a value of 12.00 ± 1.20 days. In the shaded experiment, it was the sclerotia of size 10g that emerged first with the value 12.00 ± 1.50 days (Table 1). The primordial of the sclerotia size 10g in the dark had the longest time of emergence of 35.00 ± 0.75 days (Tables 1). The differences in the illumination treatments of primordial emergence was insignificant at ($P=0.05$) while the difference in the masses of the time of primordial emergence was found to be highly significant at the same probability level.

Mean stipe length was greatest, 7.30 ± 0.71 cm in the dark and was from sclerotia size, 20g. The mean stipe length was lowest in the experimental set up in the open field, with a value of 2.06 ± 0.45 cm (Table 2). There was no significant difference in the illumination treatment on the stipe length at 5 percent probability level. The reverse is the case for the difference in sclerotia size on the stipe length at the same probability level.

The mean highest cap diameter was observed in the shaded experiment of sclerotia size 25g with a value of 9.95 ± 0.39 cm (Table 2). The least value of 2.90 ± 0.59 cm was observed in the 25g set up in the dark. The difference in these values were found to be significance and insignificant for sclerotia size and illumination treatments respectively at $P=0.05$.

Mean fresh weight production by the mushroom was highest, 28.75 ± 1.24 g in the 25g sclerotia in the shaded experiment while the least value of 8.6 ± 0.44 g was observed from the 10g sclerotia in the dark

(Table 3). The difference in weight for all the treatment was insignificant and significant for the various masses of sclerotia (P=0.05)

Mean dry weight production by the mushroom was highest, $3.76\pm0.71\text{g}$ and 3.76 ± 0.30 in 25g of both the dark and shaded experiment respectively while the least value of 1.26 ± 0.01 was observed in the 5g sclerotia in the open field. (Table 3). The difference in the illumination treatment was found to be significant as per dry weight at 5% probability level.

Table 1: Effect of illumination and sclerotia size on the time of Primordial emergence of *Pleurotus tuberregium*

Treatments	Sclerotia size(g)	Primordial emergence(days)
Dark	5	
	10	* 27.00 ± 1.25
	15	35.00 ± 0.75
	20	28.00 ± 1.25
	25	26.00 ± 1.41
Shade	5	16.00 ± 1.37
	10	13.00 ± 1.56
	15	12.00 ± 1.05
	20	30.00 ± 1.83
	25	17.00 ± 1.00
Light	5	14.00 ± 1.89
	10	16.00 ± 0.33
	15	13.00 ± 0.47
	20	15.00 ± 0.33
	25	12.00 ± 1.20
		13.00 ± 1.41

* Time of primordial emergence (days) = Mean of 5 replicates), \pm Standard error

Table 2: Effect of illumination and sclerotia size on the Morphometric measurement of *Pleurotus tuberregium*

Treatment	Sclerotia size(g)	Stipe length [cm]	Cap diameter [cm]
Dark	5	*6.97±0.55	6.96±0.45
	10	6.27±0.58	3.77±0.65
	15	6.37±0.46	5.03±0.69
	20	7.30±0.71	7.00±1.06
	25	7.03±1.68	2.90±0.59
Shade	5	4.60±0.42	5.86±0.36
	10	5.97±0.49	7.97±0.24
	15	3.57±0.33	6.33±0.72
	20	4.10±0.29	7.50±0.39
	25	7.00±1.00	9.95±0.39
Light	5	3.43±0.54	5.00±0.41
	10	2.20±0.12	4.62±0.35
	15	3.15±0.11	4.90±0.28
	20	2.52±0.28	6.04±1.30
	25	2.06±0.45	7.70±0.23

* Mean of 5 replicates,± Standard error

Table 3: Effect of illumination and sclerotia size on the sporophore yield of *Pleurotus tuberregium*.

Treatment	Sclerotia size(g)	Fresh weight (g)	Dry weight (g)
Dark	5	*9.22±0.69	1.55±0.02
	10	8.60±0.44	1.95±0.17
	15	8.62±0.53	2.34±0.27
	20	25.37±3.26	3.74±3.24
	25	24.90±1.05	3.76±0.71
Shade	5	8.80±1.20	2.39±0.56
	10	14.83±0.98	1.79±0.17
	15	16.64±0.59	1.97±0.18
	20	26.60±0.37	3.62±0.55
	25	28.75±1.24	3.76±0.30
Light	5	12.30±1.20	1.26±0.01
	10	17.55±1.38	2.35±0.25
	15	23.25±3.36	2.84±0.24
	20	18.50±1.06	3.61±0.63
	25	26.00±5.93	3.54±0.65

* Mean of 5 replicates,± Standard error

DISCUSSION

In general, there was significant difference between the illumination treatments and various sclerotia sizes for *Pleurotus tuberregium*.

Pleurotus tuberregium grew successfully with sporophore production under the different illumination condition. The different treatments and sclerotia sizes gave different results. This may be due to differences in light intensity, oxygen available, carbon dioxide presence and relative humidity (Isikhuemhen and Lebauer, 2004.)

The highest sporophore yield was at 7.80 ± 0.49 days in the shaded experiment and from sclerotia size 20g. This is due to the optimum room temperature of 25°C that as provided in the mushroom house. This observation could also be attributed to the ability of *P. tuberregium* to utilize the nutrient in soil for growth and development (Laborde, 1992).

The quick emergence of the 20g sclerotia in the open field was probably due to high oxygen concentration and optimum light intensity which are quite essential for sclerotia development. The long time of primordial emergence in the dark could be said to result from the lack of oxygen and extremely high humidity within the enclosed system. The fluctuation in the time of primordial emergence with increasing mass of the sclerotia could be attributed to the short period within which the sclerotia were soaked. But in general, the time in days of primordial emergence decreased with increasing mass of sclerotia.

The stipe with the greatest length was observed in the dark. This is due to the fact that high concentration of carbon dioxide does not favour cap development but rather stimulates elongation of the stipe. This same reason could also be responsible for the observed mould infection along the stipe in the dark. The high oxygen concentration could be said to be responsible for the quick development of cap and short stipe length that were observed.

Fluctuation in the stipe length and cap diameter was also observed which could be due to the effect of environmental factors mainly humidity and temperature on the time of primordial emergence (Laborde 1992)

Mean fresh weight was highest, 28.75 ± 1.24 g under shade and least, 8.62 ± 0.53 in the dark. The highest mean weight occurred from the sclerotia mass 25g while the least weight was from the sclerotia mass of 15g as shown in Table 3. For the illumination system, shade provides not only the optimum temperature for sclerotia development but also the high relative humidity for sporophore and mycelia production. The largest mass of 25g sclerotia gave the highest fresh weight which is by convention expected.

CONCLUSION

This experiment showed that various levels of illumination produced sporophores (fruit bodies) at different times from different masses of sclerotia. The study however showed that shade with moderate environmental conditions favours the growth, development and sporophore yield of *Pleurotus tuberregium*. More Research should therefore be further encouraged into the cultivation of mushrooms under moderate environmental conditions as this may help make available the mushroom as well as its inherent nutrients for the growing population.

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